

Study of Dual-band Resonance Characteristics of Compact Microstrip Slot Antenna

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Abstract: - The dual-band compact microstrip-slot antenna (DCMSA) is researched and proposed using IE3D software. The antenna is printed on an FR4 dielectric substrate with a permittivity of 4.4 and is powered by a 50 SMA external source with a patch introduced with two triangular and square slots to produce desired resonances. In this paper, the specific parameters such as reflection coefficient (S_{11}), bandwidth, radiation characteristics, gain, and directivity are discussed.

Keywords: Microstrip slot antenna, Dual-band response, Radiation, Gain, Bandwidth, Wireless, Triangular, slot.

1. INTRODUCTION

The antennas are suitable to satisfy the necessity for fast communication between the wireless systems, in order that they may be utilized in a broadband variety of packages in radar, navigation, satellite-tv, GPS, because of their ease of fabrication and production cost. For an antenna, with a couple of working frequencies, the adaptability to specific eventualities in wi-fi communication and radar is a prerequisite for making multiband resonance. In the literature, there were a number of articles on multiband antennas. A triple-band antenna is [1], in which the antennas are designed and used to meet the requirements of modern wi-fi communication. Several microstrip-slot antennas with low profile, conformal properties, and ease of manufacturing are investigated [2–4]. In [5], describes a microstrip-line fed tiny triple-band antenna for WLAN/WiMAX software, while [6] investigates a multi-resonator loaded antenna suitable for multiband operation. Microstrip line is used for feeding in a variety of antenna designs [7–9]. For Navy and satellite applications, a tiny multiband antenna for frequencies in the S, C, and X bands [10] is used. It has recently been demonstrated that multiband resonance may be created using coaxial feeding in a disc-patch antenna with C-shaped slots [11–13]. A tiny antenna with more than one slit for multiband operation is required that can be included for applications in mobile phones, laptops, capsules, and a variety of other small transportable devices [14]. By creating slots on the patch, a simple way for building a multiband microstrip antenna may be created [15].

Through a simulation technique, two resonant band compact microstrip antennas with double triangular and square slots on patch strips fed by microstrip-line are presented. By adopting optimised slot technique, the suggested antenna's bandwidths for the 6.1–8 GHz frequency band increased by 17 % and 14%, respectively, with a VSWR of less than 2. The length and width of the slots can be changed to modify the frequency band. This article presents and discusses the suggested design in detail.

2. IE3D OPTIMIZED DESIGN:

The suggested dual-band compact microstrip-slot antenna is depicted in Figure 1. (DCMSA). The suggested slot antenna is etched on a 1.6 mm thick FR4 material with ϵ_r of 4.4 and a delta value of 0.0001. Patch length and width (L x W) are the dimensions of the antenna (18.99 x 26.92 mm). The (Lt x Wt) of the 1/4 wavelength transformer is (10.18 x 0.66mm) and is designed for 3.5GHz. The length and width of the feed (Lf x Wf) are (10.19 x 3.35 mm), while the other measurements remain unchanged. The 50 ohm microstrip feeder is soldered to a small, finite ground plane (Lg x Wg) (35mm x 35mm). The slots are loaded into the patch with dimensions that depend on the operating wavelength. The slot length L is determined for maximum broadside performance. The microstrip lines are excited through microstrip-fed excitations for the patch antenna and slots also deviate current.

Fig. 1: Configuration of the Proposed DCMSA.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

The influence of the factors on the proposed antenna characteristics was investigated using the commercial simulation programme IE3D. Figure 2 shows a DCMSA simulation and reflection coefficient (S11) plot. The patch is electromagnetically powered via a 50 ohm connector and a microstrip line feeder. The slot placed on the patch increases the length of the current path and provides additional inductance in series. Therefore, when the resonant circuits are coupled, a large bandwidth is created. The slot aggregates current and provides additional inductance controlled by patch width. Through the simulation, we can clearly see that there are two resonant frequencies at 6.1GHz and 7.6GHz, suitable for sub-6GHz wireless communication applications.

The -10dB bandwidth is achieved at two lower resonance modes. The simulated impedance bandwidths at resonant frequencies are 17 % at 6.1 GHz and 14 % at 7.6 GHz frequencies. The trade-off between impedance bandwidth and frequency can be avoided and also improved by altering the width of the 50 ohm microstrip line. At resonant frequencies, Figure 3 depicts the simulated current distribution across the surface of the DCMSA patch. The current distribution depicts how current is redistributed across the whole radiating patch. As seen by this, the current distribution is maximum along with the triangular and square slot. Dual-band functioning is noticed as a result of the distinct slots placed on the radiation patch. Figure 4 shows the far-field radiation characteristics of the proposed antenna in 2D and 3D formats. This is essentially Broadside.

Fig. 2: Simulated reflection coefficient (S11).

Fig.3: Current distribution of DCMSA.

plot of DCMSA

(2D)

(3D)

Fig.4: Radiation Characteristics (2D & 3D) of DCMSA.

Figures 5 and 6 show the proposed DCMSA gain and field directivity plots. The maximum gain of the designed antenna is about 6dBi, each with directivity of 7.4dBi. In addition, as compared to typical antennas, the suggested antenna offers various advantages, including a lower size (compactness), better impedance matching, and a better-radiated pattern. The requirements of wireless communication systems can be met by this antenna.

Fig.5: Gain Vs frequency plot of DCMSA.**Fig.6:** Directivity Vs frequency of DCMSA.

4. CONCLUSION :

The Dualband Compact Microstrip Slot Antenna (DCMSA) is studied and proposed using IE3D software. The achieved bandwidths are 17% and 14 % for resonant frequencies respectively. The designed antennas also have better gain and broadside radiation characteristics. Such antenna finds its application in wireless systems.

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